

A multi-objective Shortage Follow Inventory (SFI) Model Involving Ramp-Type Demand, Time Varying Holding Cost and a Marketing Cost Under Neutrosophic Programming Approach

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Abstract: In the research paper we have discussed a multi-objective shortage follow deterministic inventory model where demand is ramp type and holding cost along with deterioration is time dependent. Nowadays, due to the online marketing facilities it comes to notice in different fields that various companies run a lucrative advertisement of their products through many online platforms like amazon, flipkart, snapdeal and so on. Even pre-booking goes on before the product is launched and a date for selling is fixed. Taking back-order first is highly appropriate for the seasonal items of newly launched devices like mobiles,cars, laptops, computers, automobiles etc. For the advertisement and booking the online platform a huge cost is spent by the companies. This additional charge is ultimately added to the total cost of a particular product with required proportion.In this paper we have taken all of the cost parameters as Intuitionistic triangular fuzzy numbers due to uncertainty. The minimization of total average cost is the main purpose of this model. To minimize this proposed model, we will use different methods like Fuzzy Non-Linear Programming Problem (FNLP), Fuzzy Additive Goal Programming Problem (FAGP), Intuitionistic Fuzzy Non-Linear Programming Technique (IFNLP) and Neutrosophic Non-Linear Programming Technique (NSNLP). To illustrate this proposed model the solution procedure and numerical examples have been given and sensitivity analysis for various parameters have been demonstrated lastly.

Keywords: Deterministic inventory model, multi-item, ramp-type demand, Time-varying holding cost, time-varying deterioration, neutrosophic triangular number, neutrosophic programming technique.

Introduction: Of late, the proper utilization of the inventories seeks great attention for the growth of business and every organization is trying this method to achieve their goal. Therefore, maintaining and controlling the inventories have also become a big challenge for them. They need an appropriate methodology for controlling the inventories to run their business successfully. That is why they must keep in mind the important factor of deterioration.The deterioration being a natural phenomena, its

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integral parts are change, damage, decay, spoilage etc. As the deterioration is most effective on food items, photographic films, pharmaceuticals, electronic components, drugs etc., we must count the loss caused by the deterioration in the processes of upgrading the model.

Nowadays many companies are found to run online advertisements for their products before they launch the product for sale. Pre-booking for a particular product is also invited through some on-line business platforms like amazon, snap-deal etc. This extra effect of cost must be included while developing the model. Pre-booking has great importance in understanding the demand of a particular product in the market. It has been a phenomenon in online marketing for recent years. So here we have considered all of these factors in this suggested model.

On considering the fluctuated economic circumstances, the basic assumptions of the Inventory Model (EOQ) should be upgraded at a regular interval.

Within 1957, many researchers discovered the impact of deterioration of many food items just after expiry. That is why they have taken the deterioration while developing their model. In 2007, Deng, P.S [16] developed inventory models for deterioration of items where demand is ramp-type. In 1999, Chang, H.J and Dye. C.Y [15] developed an inventory model with time varying demand and partial backlogging also included the deterioration.

It is practically impossible to take demand rate as a growing function depending on time for this in 2012, Skouri, K.; Konstantaras, I.; Manna, S.K.; Chaudhuri, K.S. [18] studied an inventory model with general ramp-type demand, the Weibull deterioration, and partial backlogging. P.S Deng in 2005 [17] considered an inventory model with ramp-type demand for items with Weibull deterioration. In 2006, S.K Manna and K.S Chaudhuri [20] described an EOQ model with time dependent deterioration rate, ramp-type demand rate, shortages and unit production cost. S. Jain and M. Kumar [5] in 2007 discovered an inventory Model with Weibull distribution deterioration, ramp-type demand, and starting with shortage. In 2010, Kun Shan Wu [2] developed an EOQ inventory model for items with ramp type demand rate, Weibull distribution deterioration and partial backlogging. In 2011, K.C Tripathy, U. Misra [3] described an EOQ model with ramp type demand and time dependent Weibull deterioration. In 2016, M. Valliathal, R. Uthayakumar [4] developed a desirable replenishment policy of an EOQ model with ramp-type demand under shortages along with non-instantaneous Weibull deteriorating items . In 2011, C.N Hung [19] developed an inventory model with deterioration, generalized type demand and back order rates.

Smarandache, F [33] established the idea of neutrosophic sets, he also presented the abstraction of The Bulgarian sets also represent the geometrical interpretation of the neutrosophic set. After that in 2014, H. Garg, M. Rani, S.P Sharma [10] discussed an Intuitionistic fuzzy optimization method to solve multi-objective reliability problems. In 2015, P. Das and T. K. Roy [14] established a multi-objective non-linear programming problem depending on neutrosophic optimization technique and its application in the field of riser design method. In intuitionistic fuzzy environment, K.S Singh, S.P Yadav [9] described the Modeling and optimization of multi objective non-linear programming problem. In 2017, Sarkar. M and Roy. T.K [11] together described truss Design Optimization with ambiguous load and stress in neutrosophic environment. S. Dey and T.K Roy [13] described the neutrosophic goal programming technique and its applications in 2017. In 2017,

Rangarajan. K, karthikeyan. K [1] described an optimization EOQ inventory model for non-instantaneous deteriorating items with time dependent holding cost and shortages along with ramp type demand rate. In 2020, with the help of triangular neutrosophic numbers, M. Mullai, R. Surya [7] described neutrosophic inventory backorder problem. In 2021, Gupta, S., Haq, A., Ali, I., Sarkar, B [23] described the importance of multi-objective optimization in logistics problem for multi-product supply chain problem using the intuitionistic fuzzy environment. Khan, M. F., Haq, A., Ahmed, A., Ali, I., in 2021 [24] described multi-objective multi-product production planning problem with the help of intuitionistic and neutrosophic fuzzy programming approach. Haq, A., Kamal, M., Gupta, S., Ali, I., in 2020 [25] discussed multi-objective production planning problem based on a case study for optimal production. Jaggi, C. K., Haq, A., Maheshwari, S., in 2020 [26] have considered a multi-objective production planning problem for a lock industry, a case study and mathematical analysis. In 2020 [27] Khan, M. A., Haq, A., Ahmed, A., discussed a multi-objective Model for Daily Diet Planning. Reliability.

In this manuscript, we proposed an inventory deterministic model where demand acts as ramp-type, deterioration and holding cost both of them have been considered as time dependent. Due to uncertainty all the cost parameters have been taken as triangular fuzzy number and triangular intuitionistic fuzzy numbers. To minimize we solved the proposed model using Fuzzy Non-Linear Programming Problem (FNLP), Fuzzy Additive Goal Programming Problem (FAGP), Intuitionistic Fuzzy Non-Linear Programming Technique (IFNLP) and Neutrosophic Non-Linear Programming Technique (NSNLP). Finally, to illustrate this proposed model the solution procedure and numerical examples have been given.

2. Mathematical Preliminaries:

2.1 Fuzzy set:

Let X be a universe of discourse. A fuzzy set which is denoted by $\tilde{A} \in X$ and is defined with the ordered pairs $\tilde{A} = \{(x, T_{\tilde{A}}(x)) : x \in X\}$.

Here $T_{\tilde{A}} : X \rightarrow [0,1]$ is a function known as truth membership function of the fuzzy set \tilde{A} .

2.2 Triangular Fuzzy Number (TFN) [28]:

Let F(R) be the set of all TFN in the set of real number R. A TFN $\tilde{A} \in F(R)$, where $\tilde{A} = (a, b, c)$ having the membership grade $\mu_{\tilde{A}} : R \rightarrow [0,1]$ is defined by

$$\mu_{\tilde{A}}(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{x - a}{b - a} & \text{For } a \leq x \leq b \\ \frac{c - x}{c - b} & \text{For } b \leq x \leq c \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Where c and a are the upper and lower limit of sustain of the set \tilde{A} .

2.3 Intuitionistic fuzzy set [29]:

Let X be an fixed set. The intuitionistic fuzzy set $\tilde{A}^I \in X$ is given by

$$\tilde{A}^I = \{ \langle x, T_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle \mid x \in X \}$$

Where $T_A : X \rightarrow [0,1]$ the truth membership is grade and $F_A : X \rightarrow [0,1]$ is the falsity membership grade.

Here $0 \leq T_A + F_A \leq 1 \forall x \in X$.

2.4 Triangular Intuitionistic Fuzzy Number (TIFN) [30]

Let a number $\tilde{A}^I = (a, b, c)(a', b, c')$ is an intuitionistic fuzzy number in R having the membership grade $\mu_{\tilde{A}^I}(x) \in [0,1]$ and non-membership grade $\partial_{\tilde{A}^I}(x) \in [0,1]$ and it is defined as

$$\mu_{\tilde{A}'}(x) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{for } x < a \\ \frac{x-a}{b-a} & \text{for } a \leq x \leq b \\ 1 & \text{for } x = b \\ \frac{c-x}{c-b} & \text{for } b \leq x \leq c \\ 0 & \text{for } x > c \end{cases}$$

$$\partial_{\tilde{A}'}(x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{for } x < a' \\ \frac{b-x}{b-a'} & \text{for } a' \leq x \leq b \\ 0 & \text{for } x = b \\ \frac{x-b}{c'-b} & \text{for } b \leq x \leq c' \\ 1 & \text{for } x > c' \end{cases}$$

Where $a' \leq a \leq b \leq c \leq c'$ and $0 \leq \mu_{\tilde{A}'}(x) + \partial_{\tilde{A}'}(x) \leq 1$.

2.5 Neutrosophic set:

Let X be the universe of discourse. The neutrosophic set $\tilde{A}^n \in X$ is given by

$$\tilde{A}^n = \{(x, T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x)) \mid x \in X\}$$

Where $T_A(x)$ is the truth membership grade, $I_A(x)$ be the indeterminacy membership grade and $F_A(x)$ be falsity membership grade. These membership functions are defined by

$$T_A(x): X \rightarrow (0, 1^+)$$

$$I_A(x): X \rightarrow (0, 1^+)$$

$$F_A(x): X \rightarrow (0, 1^+)$$

With $0 \leq \sup T_A(x) + \sup I_A(x) + \sup F_A(x) \leq 3^+$

2.6 Single valued neutrosophic set: [31]

Let X be a collection of objects called the universe of discourse. The single valued neutrosophic set $\tilde{A}^n \in X$ is defined by $\tilde{A}^n = \{(x, T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x)) \mid x \in X\}$

Here $T_A(x)$, $I_A(x)$, $F_A(x)$ are called truth, indeterminacy and falsity membership grade respectively.

These membership functions are defined by

$$T_A(x): X \rightarrow [0, 1]$$

$$I_A(x): X \rightarrow [0, 1]$$

$$F_A(x): X \rightarrow [0, 1]$$

With $0 \leq T_A(x) + I_A(x) + F_A(x) \leq 3; \forall x \in X$.

2.7 Triangular Neutrosophic Fuzzy Number (TNFN) [31].

Let $e_{\tilde{a}}, f_{\tilde{a}}, g_{\tilde{a}} \in [0, 1]$ and $a_1, a_2, a_3 \in R$ such that $a_1 \leq a_2 \leq a_3$. then the single valued triangular neutrosophic number is given by $\tilde{a} = \langle (a_1, a_2, a_3); e_{\tilde{a}}, f_{\tilde{a}}, g_{\tilde{a}} \rangle$, whose truth-membership, indeterminacy-membership and falsity-membership functions are given as follows:

$$\mu_{\tilde{A}^I}(x) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{for } x < a_1 \\ e_{\tilde{a}} \frac{x - a_1}{b_1 - a_1} & \text{for } a_1 \leq x \leq b_1 \\ e_{\tilde{a}} & \text{for } x = b_1 \\ e_{\tilde{a}} \frac{c_1 - x}{c_1 - b_1} & \text{for } b_1 \leq x \leq c_1 \\ 0 & \text{for } x > c_1 \end{cases}$$

$$\rho_{\tilde{A}^I}(x) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{for } x < a_1 \\ \frac{(b_1 - x) + f_{\tilde{a}}(x - a_1)}{b_1 - a_1} & \text{for } a_1 \leq x \leq b_1 \\ f_{\tilde{a}} & \text{for } x = b_1 \\ \frac{(x - b_1) + f_{\tilde{a}}(c_1 - x)}{c_1 - b_1} & \text{for } b_1 \leq x \leq c_1 \\ 0 & \text{for } x > c_1 \end{cases}$$

$$\partial_{\tilde{A}^I}(x) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{for } x < a_1 \\ \frac{(b_1 - x) + g_{\tilde{a}}(x - a_1)}{b_1 - a_1} & \text{for } a_1 \leq x \leq b_1 \\ g_{\tilde{a}} & \text{for } x = b_1 \\ \frac{(x - b_1) + g_{\tilde{a}}(c_1 - x)}{c_1 - b_1} & \text{for } b_1 \leq x \leq c_1 \\ 0 & \text{for } x > c_1 \end{cases}$$

Where $g_{\tilde{a}}, f_{\tilde{a}}$ and $e_{\tilde{a}}$ denote the minimum falsity-membership degree, minimum indeterminacy-membership degree and maximum truth-membership degree respectively. The single valued triangular neutrosophic number $\tilde{a} = \langle (a_1, a_2, a_3); e_{\tilde{a}}, f_{\tilde{a}}, g_{\tilde{a}} \rangle$ may express an ill-defined quantity about a_1 , which is approximately equal to a_1 .

2.8 Methods of defuzzification of TFN and TIFN.

2.8.1. Defuzzification of Triangular Fuzzy Number (TFN) [32]

If $\tilde{A} = (a_1, a_2, a_3)$ be a triangular fuzzy number then the total λ -integer value of $\tilde{A} = (a_1, a_2, a_3)$ - is given by

$$I_{\lambda}(\tilde{A}) = \lambda \frac{(a_1+a_2)}{2} + (1 - \lambda) \frac{(a_2+a_3)}{2}. \tag{1}$$

Taking $\lambda = 0.5$ we have $I_{0.5}(\tilde{A}) = \frac{a_1+2a_2+a_3}{4}$, is the approximate value of TFN number $\tilde{A} = (a_1, a_2, a_3)$.

2.8.2. Defuzzification of Triangular Intuitionistic Fuzzy Number (TIFN) [32]

Let $\tilde{A}^I = (a_1, a_2, a_3)(a'_1, a_2, a'_3)$ be a TIFN and $a'_1 \leq a_1 \leq a_2 \leq a_3 \leq a'_3$.

For defuzzification we define a score membership grade of \tilde{A}^I is given by

$$S_{\mu}(\tilde{A}^I) = \frac{a_1 + 2a_2 + a_3}{4}$$

The score non-membership function of \tilde{A}^I is given by

$$S_{\partial}(\tilde{A}^I) = \frac{a'_1 + 2a_2 + a'_3}{4}$$

Then the accuracy function of \tilde{A}^I is represented as $Acc(\tilde{A}^I)$ and is defined by

$$Acc(\tilde{A}^I) = \frac{S_{\mu}(\tilde{A}^I) + S_{\partial}(\tilde{A}^I)}{2} = \frac{a_1 + 2a_2 + a_3 + a'_1 + 2a_2 + a'_3}{8} \tag{2}$$

is the defuzzified value of the triangular intuitionistic fuzzy number $\tilde{A}^I = (a_1, a_2, a_3)(a'_1, a_2, a'_3)$.

3. Mathematical Formulation:

Some notations and assumptions are given below for the formulation of the model for i 'th item ($i=1, 2, 3, \dots, n$):.

3.1 Notations

C_{Ai} : Ordering cost per unit of time.

C_{Hi} : Holding cost per unit of time.

θ_i : Deterioration rate is depending on time.

D_i : Ramp-type Demand.

C_{pi} : the purchase cost per unit of time.

C_{di} : Deterioration cost for each item per unit of time.

C_{si} : Back order cost(Shortage cost) per unit of time.

μ_i :Parameter for demand function (ramp-type) (break point).

C_{Mi} :The marketing cost depends on demand.

T_i : Length of cycle time , $T_i \geq 0$.

t_{ii} : Procurement time, $t_{ii} \geq 0$.

$I_{ii}(t)$: The negative inventory level in the time $[0, \mu_i]$.

$I_{2i}(t)$: The positive inventory level in the time $[\mu_i, t_{1i}]$

$I_{3i}(t)$: The Inventory level with the time $[t_{ii}, T_i]$.

I_{max} : The level of maximum inventory per ordering cycle.

B_i :During the stock-out period the maximum backlogged quantity.

$I_{oi}(I_{max} + B_i)$: The order quantity for the duration of a cycle of length T_i for i 'th item.

$TAC_i(t_{ii}, T_i)$: The total average cost for each of the items.

w_i : The space of storage per unit of time.

W_i : The total space of the area.

C_{Ai}^l : Intuitionistic cost for order per unit of time.

C_{pi}^l : Intuitionistic cost for purchase per unit of time.

C_{di}^l : Intuitionistic cost for deterioration per unit of time.

C_{si}^l : Intuitionistic cost for shortage per unit of time.

C_{Hi}^l : Intuitionistic cost for holding items per unit of time.

TAC_i^l : Total Intuitionistic average cost per unit of time.

3.2 Assumptions:

i. The proposed inventory model deals with multi-item. Each item is considered as an objective function.

ii. The occurrence of replenishment is instantaneously with an infinite rate.

iii. Here we neglect the lead time. That is we are neglecting the time interval between placing the order and receiving.

iv. The demand is deterministic and it is a ramp-type function as follows

$D(t) = d_i[t - (t - \mu_i)f(t - \mu_i)]$, $d_i > 0$, $\mu_i > 0$ and Heaviside's function is given by

$$f(t - \mu_i) = \begin{cases} 0, & t < \mu_i \\ 1, & t \geq \mu_i \end{cases} \text{ where } d_i \text{ represents an initial demand and } \mu_i \text{ represents the fixed point}$$

with respect to time.

v. Deterioration rate is followed by $\theta_i(t) = \theta_i t$. $0 < \theta_i < 1$.

- vi. Inventory model starts with shortages adequate to the procurement time.
- vii. The units of deterioration are not repaired or replaced during the period.
- viii. The inventory holding cost, $C_{Hi} = h_i \cdot t$.
- ix. The ordering cost is taken as constant.
- x. The marketing cost $C_{Mi} = \alpha_i D_i^{\beta_i}$, where $\alpha_i > 0, \beta_i > 0$.

3.3 Mathematical Formulation

At time $t=0$ the system does not have any inventory at all. In the time interval $t=0$ to $t=t_{ii}$ the back order (shortages) is permitted and at time $t=t_{ii}$ the inventory is being replenished. And the quantity received, meets the back-order that has already been occurred up to the time $t=t_{ii}$. In the time $t \in [t_{ii}, T_i]$ the inventory level is reduced for demand along with deterioration. Finally at time $t=T_i$ inventory level falls down to zero. So, we can see that at time $t=0$ and $t=T_i$ the reducing system does not have any inventory at all. The graph of the above-mentioned inventory system has been given in the figure-1 given below.

Figure-1

Figure-1: Representation of Inventory model

During the negative stock period $[0, \mu_i]$ and $[\mu_i, t_{1i}]$ and the positive stock period $[t_{1i}, T_i]$, the rate of change of inventory are followed by the following differential equations.

$$\frac{dI_{1i}}{dt} = -d_i t \quad 0 \leq t \leq \mu_i; \tag{3}$$

$$\frac{dI_{2i}}{dt} = -d_i \mu_i \quad \mu_i \leq t \leq t_{1i}; \tag{4}$$

$$\frac{dI_{3i}}{dt} + \theta_i(t)I_{3i}(t) = -d_i \mu_i \quad t_{1i} \leq t \leq T_i; \tag{5}$$

Here the boundary conditions are as follow

$$I_{1i}(0) = 0, I_{2i}(t_{1i}) = I_{max}, I_{3i}(T_i) = 0; \theta_i(t) = \theta_i t \quad 0 < \theta_i < 1$$

We have from (3)

$$\int_0^t dI_{1i} = -\int_0^t d_i t dt \quad \text{where } I_{1i}(0) = 0$$

$$I_{1i}(t) = -\frac{d_i t^2}{2}, \quad 0 \leq t \leq \mu_i \tag{6}$$

We have from (4)

$$\int_{\mu_i}^t dI_{1i} = -\int_{\mu_i}^t d_i \mu_i dt, \quad \text{where } I_{1i}(\mu_i) = \frac{d_i \mu_i^2}{2} \text{ by (6)}$$

$$I_{2i}(t) = d_i \mu_i \left(\frac{\mu_i}{2} - t \right), \quad \mu_i \leq t \leq t_{1i} \tag{7}$$

Now we integrate (5) w.r.t 't' from the limit t=t to t=T and neglecting higher power of θ we get

$$I_{3i}(t) = d_i \mu_i \left[(T_i - t) + \frac{\theta_i}{6} (T_i^3 - t^3) \right] e^{-\frac{\theta_i t^2}{2}}, \quad t_{1i} \leq t \leq T_i \tag{8}$$

Now by putting t=t_{1i} we get the maximum inventory level I_{max} as follows

$$I_{max} = d_i \mu_i \left[(T_i - t_{1i}) + \frac{\theta_i}{6} (T_i^3 - t_{1i}^3) \right] e^{-\frac{\theta_i t_{1i}^2}{2}} \tag{9}$$

Total backlogged is given by

$$\begin{aligned} B &= \int_0^{\mu_i} d_i t dt + \int_{\mu_i}^{t_{1i}} d_i \mu_i dt \\ &= \frac{d_i \mu_i^2}{2} + d_i \mu_i (t_{1i} - \mu_i) \\ &= d_i \mu_i \left(\frac{\mu_i}{2} + t_{1i} - \mu_i \right) \\ &= d_i \mu_i \left(t_{1i} - \frac{\mu_i}{2} \right) \end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

So, the initial ordering quantity is given by the following expression

$$I_0 = d_i \mu_i \left[\left[(T_i - t_{1i}) + \frac{\theta_i}{6} (T_i^3 - t_{1i}^3) \right] e^{-\frac{\theta_i t_{1i}^2}{2}} + \left(t_{1i} - \frac{\mu_i}{2} \right) \right] \tag{11}$$

The types of cost are as follows

3.3.1. The ordering cost per cycle

$$O.C_i = C_{Ai} \tag{12}$$

3.3.2. The inventory holding cost per cycle

$$IHC_i = \int_{t_{1i}}^T h_i \cdot t_i \cdot d_i \cdot \mu_i \left[(T_i - t) + \frac{\theta_i}{6} (T_i^3 - t^3) \right] e^{-\frac{\theta_i t^2}{2}} dt$$

$$d_i \mu_i h_i \left[\frac{T_i}{2} (T_i^2 - t_{1i}^2) - \frac{1}{3} (T_i^3 - t_{1i}^3) + \frac{\theta_i}{6} \left\{ \frac{T_i^3}{2} (T_i^2 - t_{1i}^2) - \frac{1}{5} (T_i^5 - t_{1i}^5) \right\} - \frac{\theta_i}{2} \left\{ \frac{T_i}{4} (T_i^4 - t_{1i}^4) - \frac{1}{5} (T_i^5 - t_{1i}^5) + \frac{\theta_i}{6} \left\{ \frac{T_i^3}{4} (T_i^4 - t_{1i}^4) - \frac{1}{7} (T_i^7 - t_{1i}^7) \right\} \right\} \right] \left(\text{Neglecting the higher power of } t \text{ for the expression } e^{-\frac{\theta_i t^2}{2}} \text{ only} \right) \tag{13}$$

3.3.3. Deterioration cost for the time interval $[t_{1i}, T_i]$ for i 'th item per cycle

$$D.C_i = C_{di} \left[d_i \mu_i \left[(T_i - t_{1i}) + \frac{\theta_i}{6} (T_i^3 - t_{1i}^3) \right] e^{-\frac{\theta_i t_{1i}^2}{2}} - \int_{t_{1i}}^{T_i} d_i \mu_i dt \right] \\ = C_{di} d_i \mu_i \left[\left[(T_i - t_{1i}) + \frac{\theta_i}{6} (T_i^3 - t_{1i}^3) \right] e^{-\frac{\theta_i t_{1i}^2}{2}} + (t_{1i} - T_i) \right] \tag{14}$$

3.3.4. The Back-order cost (shortage cost) during the time period $[0, t_{1i}]$ for i 'th item per cycle

$$S.C_i = -C_{si} \left[\int_0^{\mu_i} \left(-\frac{d_i t^2}{2} \right) dt + \int_{\mu_i}^{t_{1i}} \left[d_i \mu_i \left(\frac{\mu_i}{2} - t \right) \right] dt \right] \\ = \frac{d_i \mu_i C_{si}}{6} \left[\mu_i^2 - 3\mu_i(t_{1i} - \mu_i) + 3(t_{1i}^2 - \mu_i^2) \right] \tag{15}$$

Where C_{si} is a shortage cost.

3.3.5. Total cost for purchasing an item per cycle that is max inventory as well as backlogged quantity.

$$P.C_i = d_i \mu_i C_{pi} \left[\left[(T_i - t_{1i}) + \frac{\theta_i}{6} (T_i^3 - t_{1i}^3) \right] e^{-\frac{\theta_i t_{1i}^2}{2}} + \left(t_{1i} - \frac{\mu_i}{2} \right) \right] \text{ (From (9) and (10))} \tag{16}$$

Where C_{pi} is the purchase cost.

3.3.6. The marketing cost which is basically depends on demand for the time interval $[0, T_i]$ for i 'th item per cycle is as follows

$$C_{Mi} = \int_0^{\mu_i} \alpha_i D_i^{\beta_i} dt + \int_{\mu_i}^{T_i} \alpha_i D_i^{\beta_i} dt \\ = \alpha_i \int_0^{\mu_i} (d_i t)^{\beta_i} dt + \alpha_i \int_{\mu_i}^{T_i} (d_i \mu_i)^{\beta_i} dt \\ = \alpha_i d_i^{\beta_i} \left[\frac{\mu_i^{\beta_i+1}}{\beta_i+1} + \mu_i^{\beta_i} (T_i - \mu_i) \right] \tag{17}$$

where $\alpha_i > 0, \beta_i > 0$.

Therefore, the total average cost per unit of time for each of the item per cycle is given below

$$TAC_i(t_{1i}, T_i) = \frac{1}{T_i} \left[C_{Ai} + d_i \mu_i h_i \left[\frac{T_i}{2} (T_i^2 - t_{1i}^2) - \frac{1}{3} (T_i^3 - t_{1i}^3) + \frac{\theta_i}{6} \left\{ \frac{T_i^3}{2} (T_i^2 - t_{1i}^2) - \frac{1}{5} (T_i^5 - t_{1i}^5) \right\} - \frac{\theta_i}{2} \left\{ \frac{T_i}{4} (T_i^4 - t_{1i}^4) - \frac{1}{5} (T_i^5 - t_{1i}^5) + \frac{\theta_i}{6} \left\{ \frac{T_i^3}{4} (T_i^4 - t_{1i}^4) - \frac{1}{7} (T_i^7 - t_{1i}^7) \right\} \right\} \right] \right] \\ + C_{di} d_i \mu_i \left[\left[(T_i - t_{1i}) + \frac{\theta_i}{6} (T_i^3 - t_{1i}^3) \right] e^{-\frac{\theta_i t_{1i}^2}{2}} + (t_{1i} - T_i) \right] \\ + \frac{d_i \mu_i C_{si}}{6} \left[\mu_i^2 - 3\mu_i(t_{1i} - \mu_i) + 3(t_{1i}^2 - \mu_i^2) \right] + d_i \mu_i C_{pi} \left[\left[(T_i - t_{1i}) + \frac{\theta_i}{6} (T_i^3 - t_{1i}^3) \right] e^{-\frac{\theta_i t_{1i}^2}{2}} + \left(t_{1i} - \frac{\mu_i}{2} \right) \right] \\ + \alpha_i d_i^{\beta_i} \left[\frac{\mu_i^{\beta_i+1}}{\beta_i+1} + \mu_i^{\beta_i} (T_i - \mu_i) \right] \tag{18}$$

We consider the average total cost of multi objective inventory model (MOIM) as follows

Minimize $\{TAC_1(t_{11}, T_1), TAC_2(t_{12}, T_2), \dots, TAC_n(t_{1n}, T_n)\}$ for $i=1,2,3, 4, \dots, n$

Subject to: $\sum_{i=1}^n w_i Q_i \leq W$

Where,

$$TAC_i(t_i, T_i) \text{ represented by (18) and } Q_i = d_i \mu_i \left[\left[(T_i - t_{1i}) + \frac{\theta_i}{6} (T_i^3 - t_{1i}^3) \right] e^{-\frac{\theta_i t_{1i}^2}{2}} + \left(t_{1i} - \frac{\mu_i}{2} \right) \right] \quad (19)$$

4. Fuzzy Model:

To deal with Uncertainties let us take all the cost parameters as triangular Intuitionistic fuzzy numbers.

Here we consider the cost parameters as TIFN

$$\widetilde{C}_{At}^I = (C_{Ai1}^I, C_{Ai2}^I, C_{Ai3}^I)(C_{Ai1}^{II}, C_{Ai2}^{II}, C_{Ai3}^{II}) \quad \text{Where } C_{Ai1}^{II} \leq C_{Ai1}^I \leq C_{Ai2}^I \leq C_{Ai2}^{II} \leq C_{Ai3}^{II}$$

$$\widetilde{C}_{P_i}^I = (C_{pi1}^I, C_{pi2}^I, C_{pi3}^I)(C_{pi1}^{II}, C_{pi2}^{II}, C_{pi3}^{II}) \quad \text{Where } C_{pi1}^{II} \leq C_{pi1}^I \leq C_{pi2}^I \leq C_{pi2}^{II} \leq C_{pi3}^{II}$$

$$\widetilde{C}_{d_i}^I = (C_{di1}^I, C_{di2}^I, C_{di3}^I)(C_{di1}^{II}, C_{di2}^{II}, C_{di3}^{II}) \quad \text{Where } C_{di1}^{II} \leq C_{di1}^I \leq C_{di2}^I \leq C_{di2}^{II} \leq C_{di3}^{II}$$

$$\widetilde{C}_{s_i}^I = (C_{si1}^I, C_{si2}^I, C_{si3}^I)(C_{si1}^{II}, C_{si2}^{II}, C_{si3}^{II}) \quad \text{Where } C_{si1}^{II} \leq C_{si1}^I \leq C_{si2}^I \leq C_{si2}^{II} \leq C_{si3}^{II}$$

$$\widetilde{h}_i^I = (h_{i1}^I, h_{i2}^I, h_{i3}^I)(h_{i1}^{II}, h_{i2}^{II}, h_{i3}^{II}) \quad \text{Where } h_{i1}^{II} \leq h_{i1}^I \leq h_{i2}^I \leq h_{i2}^{II} \leq h_{i3}^{II}$$

$$\widetilde{d}_i^I = (d_{i1}^I, d_{i2}^I, d_{i3}^I)(d_{i1}^{II}, d_{i2}^{II}, d_{i3}^{II}) \quad \text{Where } d_{i1}^{II} \leq d_{i1}^I \leq d_{i2}^I \leq d_{i2}^{II} \leq d_{i3}^{II}$$

Our multi-objective inventory model (3.3.17) becomes Intuitionistic Fuzzy model as follows

$$\text{Minimize } \{ (\widetilde{TAC}_1^I(t_{11}, T_1), \widetilde{TAC}_2^I(t_{12}, T_2), \dots, \dots, \dots, \widetilde{TAC}_n^I(t_{1n}, T_n) \}$$

$$\text{Subject to: } \sum_{i=1}^n w_i Q_i \leq W \quad \text{for } i=1, 2, 3, 4, \dots, n$$

Where,

$$\begin{aligned} \widetilde{TAC}_i(t_{1i}, T_i) = & \frac{1}{T_i} [\widetilde{C}_{At}^I + \widetilde{d}_i^I \mu_i \widetilde{h}_i^I \left[\frac{T_i}{2} (T_i^2 - t_{1i}^2) - \frac{1}{3} (T_i^3 - t_{1i}^3) + \frac{\theta_i}{6} \left\{ \frac{T_i^3}{2} (T_i^2 - t_{1i}^2) - \frac{1}{5} (T_i^5 - t_{1i}^5) \right\} - \right. \\ & \left. \frac{\theta_i}{2} \left\{ \frac{T_i}{4} (T_i^4 - t_{1i}^4) - \frac{1}{5} (T_i^5 - t_{1i}^5) + \frac{\theta_i}{6} \left\{ \frac{T_i^3}{4} (T_i^4 - t_{1i}^4) - \frac{1}{7} (T_i^7 - t_{1i}^7) \right\} \right\} \right] + \widetilde{C}_{d_i}^I \widetilde{d}_i^I \mu_i \left[(T_i - t_{1i}) + \right. \\ & \left. \frac{\theta_i}{6} (T_i^3 - t_{1i}^3) \right] e^{-\frac{\theta_i t_{1i}^2}{2}} + (t_{1i} - T_i) + \frac{\widetilde{d}_i^I \mu_i \widetilde{C}_{s_i}^I}{6} [\mu_i^2 - 3\mu_i(t_{1i} - \mu_i) + 3(t_{1i}^2 - \mu_i^2)] + \widetilde{d}_i^I \mu_i \widetilde{C}_{P_i}^I \left[(T_i - t_{1i}) + \right. \\ & \left. \frac{\theta_i}{6} (T_i^3 - t_{1i}^3) \right] e^{-\frac{\theta_i t_{1i}^2}{2}} + \left(t_{1i} - \frac{\mu_i}{2} \right) + \alpha_i (\widetilde{d}_i^I)^{\beta_i} \left[\frac{\mu_i^{\beta_i+1}}{\beta_i+1} + \mu_i^{\beta_i} (T_i - \mu_i) \right] \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{And } Q_i = \widetilde{d}_i^I \mu_i \left[\left[(T_i - t_{1i}) + \frac{\theta_i}{6} (T_i^3 - t_{1i}^3) \right] e^{-\frac{\theta_i t_{1i}^2}{2}} + \left(t_{1i} - \frac{\mu_i}{2} \right) \right] \quad (20)$$

Using the defuzzification technique (1) our Intuitionistic fuzzy parameters $(\widetilde{C}_{At}^I, \widetilde{C}_{P_i}^I, \widetilde{C}_{d_i}^I, \widetilde{C}_{s_i}^I, \widetilde{h}_i^I, \widetilde{d}_i^I)$ transforming into crisp value $(\widehat{C}_{At}^I, \widehat{C}_{P_i}^I, \widehat{C}_{d_i}^I, \widehat{C}_{s_i}^I, \widehat{h}_i^I, \widehat{d}_i^I)$

With these our Fuzzy Intuitionistic model transforming into crisp model as given as below

$$\text{Minimize } \{ (\widehat{TAC}_1^I(t_{11}, T_1), \widehat{TAC}_2^I(t_{12}, T_2), \dots, \dots, \dots, \widehat{TAC}_n^I(t_{1n}, T_n) \}$$

$$\text{Subject to: } \sum_{i=1}^n w_i Q_i \leq W \quad \text{for } i=1,2,3,4, \dots, n$$

Where,

$$\begin{aligned} \widehat{TAC}_i(t_{1i}, T_i) = & \frac{1}{T_i} [\widehat{C}_{At}^I + \widehat{d}_i^I \mu_i \widehat{h}_i^I \left[\frac{T_i}{2} (T_i^2 - t_{1i}^2) - \frac{1}{3} (T_i^3 - t_{1i}^3) + \frac{\theta_i}{6} \left\{ \frac{T_i^3}{2} (T_i^2 - t_{1i}^2) - \frac{1}{5} (T_i^5 - t_{1i}^5) \right\} - \right. \\ & \left. \frac{\theta_i}{2} \left\{ \frac{T_i}{4} (T_i^4 - t_{1i}^4) - \frac{1}{5} (T_i^5 - t_{1i}^5) + \frac{\theta_i}{6} \left\{ \frac{T_i^3}{4} (T_i^4 - t_{1i}^4) - \frac{1}{7} (T_i^7 - t_{1i}^7) \right\} \right\} \right] + \widehat{C}_{d_i}^I \widehat{d}_i^I \mu_i \left[(T_i - t_{1i}) + \right. \\ & \left. \frac{\theta_i}{6} (T_i^3 - t_{1i}^3) \right] e^{-\frac{\theta_i t_{1i}^2}{2}} + (t_{1i} - T_i) + \frac{\widehat{d}_i^I \mu_i \widehat{C}_{s_i}^I}{6} [\mu_i^2 - 3\mu_i(t_{1i} - \mu_i) + 3(t_{1i}^2 - \mu_i^2)] + \widehat{d}_i^I \mu_i \widehat{C}_{P_i}^I \left[(T_i - t_{1i}) + \right. \\ & \left. \frac{\theta_i}{6} (T_i^3 - t_{1i}^3) \right] e^{-\frac{\theta_i t_{1i}^2}{2}} + \left(t_{1i} - \frac{\mu_i}{2} \right) + \alpha_i (\widehat{d}_i^I)^{\beta_i} \left[\frac{\mu_i^{\beta_i+1}}{\beta_i+1} + \mu_i^{\beta_i} (T_i - \mu_i) \right] \end{aligned}$$

$$\frac{\theta_i}{6} (T_i^3 - t_{1i}^3) \left] e^{-\frac{\theta_i t_{1i}^2}{2}} + (t_{1i} - T_i) \right] + \frac{\widehat{d}_i^l \mu_i \widehat{C}_{pi}}{6} [\mu_i^2 - 3\mu_i(t_{1i} - \mu_i) + 3(t_{1i}^2 - \mu_i^2)] + \widehat{d}_i^l \mu_i \widehat{C}_{pi} \left[(T_i - t_{1i}) + \frac{\theta_i}{6} (T_i^3 - t_{1i}^3) \right] e^{-\frac{\theta_i t_{1i}^2}{2}} + \left(t_{1i} - \frac{\mu_i}{2} \right) \right] + \alpha_i (\widehat{d}_i^l)^{\beta_i} \left[\frac{\mu_i^{\beta_i+1}}{\beta_i+1} + \mu_i^{\beta_i} (T_i - \mu_i) \right]$$

And $Q_i = \widehat{d}_i^l \mu_i \left[(T_i - t_{1i}) + \frac{\theta_i}{6} (T_i^3 - t_{1i}^3) \right] e^{-\frac{\theta_i t_{1i}^2}{2}} + \left(t_{1i} - \frac{\mu_i}{2} \right)$ (21)

Here, w_i and W_i represent space per unit of time and the total area space for i 'th item respectively for storing inventory.

5. New Techniques to Solve a Multi-Objective Inventory Model.

To solving the above multi objective inventory (21) problem we consider single objective at a time and the others objectives are ignored.

Applying this technique we find out the value of each objective function separately and by tracking this technique we will formulate the following pay-of-matrix.

$$\begin{matrix} & TAC_1(t_{11}, T_1) & TAC_2(t_{12}, T_2) & \dots & \dots & \dots & TAC_n(t_{1n}, T_n) \\ \begin{matrix} (t_{11}^1, T_1^1) \\ (t_{12}^2, T_2^2) \\ \dots & \dots & \dots \\ (t_{1n}^n, T_n^n) \end{matrix} & \left[\begin{matrix} TAC_1^*(t_{11}^1, T_1^1) & TAC_2(t_{11}^1, T_1^1) & \dots & \dots & TAC_n(t_{11}^1, T_1^1) \\ TAC_1(t_{12}^2, T_2^2) & TAC_2^*(t_{12}^2, T_2^2) & \dots & \dots & TAC_n(t_{12}^2, T_2^2) \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ TAC_1(t_{1n}^n, T_n^n) & TAC_2(t_{1n}^n, T_n^n) & \dots & \dots & TAC_n^*(t_{1n}^n, T_n^n) \end{matrix} \right] \end{matrix}$$

Now we set $U_r^T = \max\{TAC_r(t_{2i}^i, T_i^i), i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n\}$, for $r = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$

And $L_r^T = \{TAC_r^*(t_{1r}^r, T_r^r), r = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n\}$

Where $L_r^T \leq TAC_r(t_{2i}^i, T_i^i) \leq U_r^T$; for $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$; and $k = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$; (22)

5.1. Fuzzy Non-Linear Programming Problems (FNLP) and Fuzzy Additive Goal Programming Problems (FAGP)

Now we take for simplicity a linear fuzzy membership function $\mu_{TAC_r}(TAC_r(t_{1r}, T_r))$ for the r 'th objective function $TAC_r(t_{1r}, T_r)$ as follows.

$$\mu_{TAC_r}(TAC_r(t_{1r}, T_r)) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{for } TAC_r(t_{1r}, T_r) \leq L_r^T \\ \frac{U_r^T - TAC_r(t_{1r}, T_r)}{U_r^T - L_r^T} & \text{for } L_r^T \leq TAC_r(t_{1r}, T_r) \leq U_r^T \\ 0 & \text{for } TAC_r(t_{1r}, T_r) \geq U_r^T \end{cases} \quad (23)$$

For $r = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$;

Using (23) we established the fuzzy non-linear programming problems (FNLP).

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Max} = p \\ & \text{Subject to,} \\ & p(U_r^T - L_r^T) + TAC_r(t_{1r}, T_r) \leq U_r^T \quad \text{For } r = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n \\ & 0 \leq p \leq 1, \quad t_{1r} \geq 0, T_r \geq 0; \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

And the same restriction and constraints as in the problem (21)

Now we formulated Fuzzy additive goal programming (FAGP) based on max-additive operator as given below:

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Max } \sum_{r=1}^n \frac{U_r^T - TAC_r(t_{1r}, T_r)}{U_r^T - L_r^T} \\ & \text{Subject to, } 0 \leq \mu_{TAC_r}(TAC_r(t_{1r}, T_r)) \leq 1, \text{ for } r=1,2,3,\dots,n \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

And the same restriction and constraints as in the problem (21)

Now we are finding the optimal solution for the above reduced problem (24) and (25) with the help of above FNLP and FAGP method.

5.2. Weighted Fuzzy Non-Linear Programming technique and Weighted Fuzzy Goal Programming Technique (WFNLP AND WFAGP):

We are taking here a positive weight ω_r for every objective ($TAC_r(t_{1r}, T_r)$)

(Where $r=1,2,3,\dots,n$) and $\sum_{r=1}^n \omega_r = 1$.

Having these normalized weights and the membership function (23), the FNLP technique becomes

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Max } p \\ & \text{Subject to,} \\ & \omega_r \cdot \mu_{TAC_r}(TAC_r(t_{1r}, T_r)) \geq p \quad \text{For } r=1, 2, 3, \dots, n \\ & 0 \leq p \leq 1, \quad t_{1r} \geq 0, T_r \geq 0 \text{ and } \sum_{r=1}^n \omega_r = 1. \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

And the same restriction and constraints as in the problem (21)

Having these normalized weights and the membership function (23), the FAGP technique becomes

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Max } \sum_{r=1}^n \omega_k \cdot \mu_{TAC_r}(TAC_r(t_{1r}, T_r)) \\ & \text{Subject to, } 0 \leq \mu_{TAC_r}(TAC_r(t_{1r}, T_r)) \leq 1, \text{ for } r=1,2,3,\dots,n \text{ and} \\ & t_{1r} \geq 0, T_r \geq 0; \sum_{r=1}^n \omega_r = 1 \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

And the same restriction and constraints as in the problem (21)

Now we are finding the optimal solution with the help of above WFNLP and WFAGP method.

5.3. Intuitionistic Fuzzy Non-Linear Programming (IFNLP) Method:

Using (5.1) here we have considered a linear membership grade (Truth membership) and a nonlinear membership grade (Falsity membership).

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_{TAC_r}(TAC_r(t_{1r}, T_r)) &= \begin{cases} 1 & \text{for } TAC_r(t_{1r}, T_r) \leq L_r^T \\ \frac{U_r^T - TAC_r(t_{1r}, T_r)}{U_r^T - L_r^T} & \text{for } L_r^T \leq TAC_r(t_{1r}, T_r) \leq U_r^T \\ 0 & \text{for } TAC_r(t_{1r}, T_r) \geq U_r^T \end{cases} \\ \partial_{TAC_r}(TAC_r(t_{1r}, T_r)) &= \begin{cases} 1 & \text{for } TAC_r(t_{1r}, T_r) \geq U_r^T \\ \frac{TAC_r(t_{1r}, T_r) - L_r^T}{U_r^T - L_r^T} & \text{for } L_r^T \leq TAC_r(t_{1r}, T_r) \leq U_r^T \\ 0 & \text{for } TAC_r(t_{1r}, T_r) \leq L_r^T \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

For $r=1,2,3,\dots,n$;

After getting the membership function (truth membership) and non-membership functions (falsity membership value) for every objective function and using (22), the original problem (21) can also be formulated as a crisp model as given below.

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Max } \alpha_1, \text{ Min } \beta_1 \\ & \text{Subject to } \mu_{TAC_r}(TAC_r(t_{1r}, T_r)) \geq \alpha_1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_{TAC_r}(TAC_r(t_{1r}, T_r)) &\leq \beta_1 \\ \alpha_1 + \beta_1 &\leq 1; \alpha_1 \geq \beta_1; \alpha_1, \beta_1 \geq 0; t_{1r} \geq 0, T_r \geq 0; \end{aligned} \tag{29}$$

And the same restriction and constraints as in the problem (21)

For $r=1,2,3,\dots,n$

Where α_1 denotes the minimal accepting degree of the objectives and the constraints and β_1 is the maximal rejection degree of the objectives and constraints. The above IFNLP model transforms into the following crisp (non-fuzzy) model

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{Max } (\alpha_1 - \beta_1) \\ &\text{Subject to, } \mu_{TAC_r}(TAC_r(t_{1r}, T_r)) \geq \alpha_1 \\ &\quad \partial_{TAC_r}(TAC_r(t_{1r}, T_r)) \leq \beta_1 \\ &\quad \alpha_1 + \beta_1 \leq 1; \alpha_1 \geq \beta_1, \alpha_1, \beta_1 \in [0,1]; t_{1r} \geq 0, T_r \geq 0; \end{aligned} \tag{30}$$

And the same restriction and constraints as in the problem (21)

For $r=1,2,3,\dots,n$

5.4. Neutrosophic Non-Linear Programming (NSNLP) technique.

By using (22), we define a linear type truth membership, indeterminacy membership, falsity membership functions as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_{TAC_r}(TAC_r(t_{1r}, T_r)) &= \begin{cases} 1 & \text{for } TAC_r(t_{1r}, T_r) \leq L_r^T \\ \frac{U_r^T - TAC_r(t_{1r}, T_r)}{U_r^T - L_r^T} & \text{for } L_r^T \leq TAC_r(t_{1r}, T_r) \leq U_r^T \\ 0 & \text{for } TAC_r(t_{1r}, T_r) \geq U_r^T \end{cases} \\ \rho_{TAC_r}(TAC_r(t_{1r}, T_r)) &= \begin{cases} 1 & \text{for } TAC_r(t_{1r}, T_r) \leq L_r^I \\ \frac{U_r^I - TAC_r(t_{1r}, T_r)}{U_r^I - L_r^I} & \text{for } L_r^I \leq TAC_r(t_{1r}, T_r) \leq U_r^I \\ 0 & \text{for } TAC_r(t_{1r}, T_r) \geq U_r^I \end{cases} \\ \partial_{TAC_r}(TAC_r(t_{1r}, T_r)) &= \begin{cases} 1 & \text{for } TAC_r(t_{1r}, T_r) \geq U_r^F \\ \frac{TAC_r(t_{1r}, T_r) - L_r^F}{U_r^F - L_r^F} & \text{for } L_r^F \leq TAC_r(t_{1r}, T_r) \leq U_r^F \\ 0 & \text{for } TAC_r(t_{1r}, T_r) \leq L_r^F \end{cases} \end{aligned} \tag{31}$$

For $r=1,2,3, \dots, n$

Where,

$$\begin{aligned} U_r^F &= U_r^T \text{ and } L_r^F = L_r^T + t(U_r^T - L_r^T) \\ L_r^I &= L_r^T \text{ and } U_r^I = L_r^T + s(U_r^T - L_r^T); s, t \in [0,1] \end{aligned}$$

After getting the membership function (truth membership), non-membership function (falsity membership value) and indeterminacy membership function for every objective function and using (22), our original problem (21) transform into a crisp model as given by

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{Max } \alpha, \text{ Min } \beta, \text{ Max } \gamma \\ &\text{Subject to } \mu_{TAC_r}(TAC_r(t_{1r}, T_r)) \geq \alpha; \\ &\quad \partial_{TAC_r}(TAC_r(t_{1r}, T_r)) \leq \beta; \\ &\quad \rho_{TAC_r}(TAC_r(t_{1r}, T_r)) \geq \gamma; \\ &\quad \alpha + \beta + \gamma \leq 3; \alpha \geq \beta; \alpha \geq \gamma; \alpha, \beta, \gamma \in [0,1]; t_{1r} \geq 0, T_r \geq 0; \end{aligned} \tag{32}$$

And by taking into consideration the same restrictions and constraints as in the equation (21)

For $r=1,2,3,\dots,n$

Where α denotes the minimal accepting degree for the objectives as well as for the constraints and β is stands for maximal rejection degree for the objectives as well as for the constraints and γ is the degree of indeterminacy. Above NSNLP model transforms into a crisp (non-fuzzy) model as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{Maximize } (\alpha - \beta + \gamma) \\
 & \text{Subject to } TAC_r(t_{1r}, T_r) + (U_r^T - L_r^T)\alpha \leq U_r^T; \\
 & TAC_r(t_{1r}, T_r) + (U_r^I - L_r^I)\gamma \leq U_r^I; \\
 & TAC_r(t_{1r}, T_r) - (U_r^F - L_r^F)\beta \leq L_r^F; \\
 & \alpha + \beta + \gamma \leq 3; \quad \alpha \geq \beta; \alpha \geq \gamma; \alpha, \beta, \gamma \in [0,1]; t_{1r} \geq 0, T_r \geq 0; \text{ For } r=1,2,3,\dots,n \tag{33}
 \end{aligned}$$

And the same restriction and constraints in the equation (21)

Where,

$$\begin{aligned}
 U_r^F &= U_r^T \text{ and } L_r^F = L_r^T + t(U_r^T - L_r^T) \\
 L_r^I &= L_r^T \text{ and } U_r^I = L_r^T + s(U_r^T - L_r^T)
 \end{aligned}$$

Where $s, t \in [0,1]$

6. Numerical Examples

To illustrate the multi objective inventory model where demand is ramp-type, deterioration and back-order are variable, we have considered the following example. Here we have taken the cost parameters as TIFN and some parameters are taken as crisp.

Let total area space $W=5000 \text{ m}^2$

$$\text{Minimize } \{ \widehat{TAC}_1^I(t_{11}, T_1), \widehat{TAC}_2^I(t_{12}, T_2) \}$$

$$\text{Subject to: } \sum_{i=1}^n w_i Q_i \leq W \quad \text{where } i=1,2$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \widehat{TAC}_i^I(t_{1i}, T_i) &= \frac{1}{T_i} [\widehat{C}_{Ai}^I + \widehat{d}_i \mu_i \widehat{h}_i] \left[\frac{T_i}{2} (T_i^2 - t_{1i}^2) - \frac{1}{3} (T_i^3 - t_{1i}^3) + \frac{\theta_i}{6} \left\{ \frac{T_i^3}{2} (T_i^2 - t_{1i}^2) - \frac{1}{5} (T_i^5 - t_{1i}^5) \right\} - \right. \\
 & \left. \frac{\theta_i}{2} \left\{ \left\{ \frac{T_i}{4} (T_i^4 - t_{1i}^4) - \frac{1}{5} (T_i^5 - t_{1i}^5) + \frac{\theta_i}{6} \left\{ \frac{T_i^3}{4} (T_i^4 - t_{1i}^4) - \frac{1}{7} (T_i^7 - t_{1i}^7) \right\} \right\} \right\} \right] + \widehat{C}_{di}^I \widehat{d}_i \mu_i \left[(T_i - t_{1i}) + \right. \\
 & \left. \frac{\theta_i}{6} (T_i^3 - t_{1i}^3) \right] e^{-\frac{\theta_i t_{1i}^2}{2}} + (t_{1i} - T_i) \left] + \frac{\widehat{d}_i \mu_i \widehat{C}_{si}^I}{6} [\mu_i^2 - 3\mu_i (t_{1i} - \mu_i) + 3(t_{1i}^2 - \mu_i^2)] + \widehat{d}_i \mu_i \widehat{C}_{pi}^I \left[(T_i - t_{1i}) + \right. \\
 & \left. \frac{\theta_i}{6} (T_i^3 - t_{1i}^3) \right] e^{-\frac{\theta_i t_{1i}^2}{2}} + \left(t_{1i} - \frac{\mu_i}{2} \right) \left] + \alpha_i (\widehat{d}_i)^{\beta_i} \left[\frac{\mu_i^{\beta_i+1}}{\beta_i+1} + \mu_i^{\beta_i} (T_i - \mu_i) \right] \right] \\
 \text{And } Q_i &= \widehat{d}_i \mu_i \left[(T_i - t_{1i}) + \frac{\theta_i}{6} (T_i^3 - t_{1i}^3) \right] e^{-\frac{\theta_i t_{1i}^2}{2}} + \left(t_{1i} - \frac{\mu_i}{2} \right) \right] \quad \text{for } i=1,2
 \end{aligned}$$

Here we take the crisp values of cost parameters

For the first objective function (i.e., 1st item), $\alpha_1 = 0.55, \beta_1 = 0.45, \mu_1 = 0.26, \theta_2 = 0.08, w_1 = 4$

For the second objective function (i.e., 2nd item), $\alpha_2 = 0.55, \beta_2 = 0.45, \mu_2 = 0.26, \theta_2 = 0.08, w_2 = 4, Q=5000$

Here we take the cost parameters as triangular intuitionistic fuzzy numbers.

Table-1

Cost parameters	Items	
	1 st item's cost (TIFN)	2 nd item's cost (TIFN)
\tilde{c}_{At}^I	((125, 130, 135) (122,130,140))	((130, 135, 140) (126,135,142))
\tilde{c}_{Pt}^I	((17,19,23) (15,19,25))	((18,20,22) (16,20,24))
\tilde{c}_{dt}^I	((12,15,18) (10,15,20))	((13,16,17) (11,16,22))
\tilde{c}_{st}^I	((5,7,10) (4,7,13))	((7,9,12) (6,9,14))
\tilde{h}_t^I	((0.50,1,2) (0.25,1,3))	((1,1.5,2) (0.5,1.5,4))
\tilde{d}_t^I	((115, 120, 125) (112,120,130))	((120, 125, 130) (118,125,135))

Optimum solution by different methods (FNLP, FAGP, WFNLP, WFAGP, IFNLP, NSNLP)

Table-2

METHODS	$TAC_1^*(t_{11}^*, T_1^*)$	t_{11}^*	T_1^*	$TAC_2^*(t_{12}^*, T_2^*)$	t_{12}^*	T_2^*
FNLP	682.3808	0.393911	1.085939	728.2010	0.215405	1.015091
FAGP	682.3808	0.393911	1.085939	728.2010	0.2149483	1.015632
WFNLP	682.3809	0.24049	1.086356	728.2010	0.2141508	1.015686
WFAGP	682.3809	0.24049	1.086356	728.2010	0.2141508	1.015686
IFNLP	682.3808	0.2393911	1.085939	728.2010	0.2143809	1.016013
NSNLP	682.3808	0.2393911	1.085939	728.2010	0.2153121	1.014994

From the figure-2 it is easy to say the values of the average total cost of two-items are almost same. FNLP, FAGP, IFNLP and NSNLP gives the equal value of the total cost but WFNLP and WFAGP gives slide difference value of total cost.

Graph for the average total cost in new methods.

Now we are willing to find what different happen in total average cost if we take the cost parameters as triangular fuzzy numbers instead of the triangular intuitionistic numbers.

Table-3

Methods	Cost parameters	Triangular Intuitionistic fuzzy numbers (1 st Item)	Triangular fuzzy numbers (1 st Item)	Triangular Intuitionistic fuzzy numbers (2 nd Item)	Triangular fuzzy numbers (2 nd Item)	Total average cost (1 st Item) (For TIFN)	Total average cost (2 nd Item) (For TIFN)	Total average cost (1 st Item) (For TFN)	Total average cost (2 nd Item) (For TFN)
FNL FAGP IFNL NSNL P	\tilde{C}_{Ai}^I	(125,130,135) (122,130,140)	(125,130,135)	(130, 135, 140) (126,135,142)	(130,135,140)	682.3808	728.2010	665.6314	725.6821
	\tilde{C}_{Pi}^I	(17,19,23) (15,19,25)	(17,19,21)	(18,20,22) (16,20,24)	(18,20,22)				
	\tilde{C}_{di}^I	(12,15,18) (10,15,20)	(12,15,18)	(13,16,17) (11,16,22)	(14,16,18)				
	\tilde{C}_{si}^I	(5,7,10) (4,7,13)	(5,7,9)	(7,9,12) (6,9,14)	(7,9,11)				
	\tilde{h}_i^I	(0.50,1,2) (0.25,1,3)	(0.7,1,1.3)	(1,1.5,2) (0.5,1.5,4)	(1,1.5,2)				
	\tilde{d}_i^I	(115, 120, 125) (112,120,130)	(115,120,125)	(120, 125, 130) (118,125,135)	(120,125,130)				

For FNL, FAGP, IFNL, NSNL technique

In this section (Figure-3) we analyze the average of total minimum cost for triangular fuzzy number and Intuitionistic fuzzy number.

Here we observe that the total average cost of two item is bigger when we are taking triangular Intuitionistic fuzzy number instead of the triangular fuzzy number.

Figure-3 Graph for the total average costs of two items With TIFN and TFN.

8. Sensitivity Analysis

Now we will discuss how the total average cost changing on the basis of change of ordering cost, purchasing cost by FNLP, FAGP, WFNLP, WFAGP, IFNLP, NSFNLP technique.

For first objective function (i.e., 1st item) we are taking, $\alpha_1 = 0.55, \beta_1 = 0.45, \mu_1 = 0.26, \theta_2 = 0.08, w_1 = 4, C_{p1} = 19, C_{d1} = 15, C_{s1} = 7, d_1 = 120, h_1 = 1$

For second objective function (i.e., 2nd item) we are taking, $\alpha_2 = 0.55, \beta_2 = 0.45, \mu_2 = 0.26, \theta_2 = 0.08, C_{p2} = 20, C_{d2} = 16, C_{s2} = 9, d_2 = 125, h_2 = 1.5, w_2 = 4, Q = 5000$

TABLE-4

Method s	ORDERING COST FOR 1 st ITEM	ORDERING COST FOR 2 nd ITEM	TAC ₁ ($t_{01}^*, t_{11}^*, T_1^*$)	TAC ₂ ($t_{02}^*, t_{12}^*, T_2^*$)
FNLP	120	125	656.5169	715.6611
	125	130	661.1160	720.7620
	130	135	665.6314	725.6820
FAGP	120	125	656.5169	715.6611
	125	130	661.1160	720.7620
	130	135	665.6314	725.6820
WFNLP	120	125	656.5245	715.7559
	125	130	661.1160	720.7620
	130	135	665.6314	725.6820
WFAGP	120	125	656.5245	715.7559
	125	130	661.1160	720.7620
	130	135	665.6314	725.6820
IFNLP	120	125	656.5245	715.7559
	125	130	661.1160	720.7620
	130	135	665.6314	725.6820
NSNLP	120	125	656.5169	715.6611
	125	130	661.1160	720.7620
	130	135	665.6314	725.6820

Here we have considered the weighs (0.7, 0.3) for both of the methods WFNLP, WFAGP.

Graph for the average of total cost of 1st item by different Technique with different ordering cost.

Graph for the average of total cost of 2nd item by different Technique with different ordering cost.

From the above figures (Figure-4, Figure-5), we can see that when ordering costs increase, the corresponding total average cost also increases.

For the first objective function (i.e., 1st item) we are taking, $\alpha_1 = 0.55, \beta_1 = 0.45, \mu_1 = 0.26, \theta_2 = 0.08, w_1 = 4, C_{A1} = 130, C_{d1} = 15, C_{s1} = 7, d_1 = 120, h_1 = 1$

For the second objective function (i.e., 2nd item) we are taking, $\alpha_2 = 0.55, \beta_2 = 0.45, \mu_2 = 0.26, \theta_2 = 0.08, C_{A2} = 135, C_{d2} = 16, C_{s2} = 9, d_2 = 125, h_2 = 1.5, w_2 = 4, Q = 5000$

TABLE-5

Methods	PURCHASE COST FOR 1 st ITEM	PURCHASE COST FOR 2 nd ITEM	TAC ₁ ($t_{01}^*, t_{11}^*, T_1^*$)	TAC ₂ ($t_{02}^*, t_{12}^*, T_2^*$)
FNLP	8	14	349.5078	550.1597
	9	15	378.7996	579.7397
	10	16	407.9882	609.2553
FAGP	8	14	349.5078	550.1597
	9	15	378.7996	579.7397
	10	16	407.9882	609.2553
WFNLP	8	14	351.6440	550.1597
	9	15	380.9453	579.7397
	10	16	410.1524	609.2553

WFAGP	8	14	349.5078	550.1597
	9	15	378.7996	579.7397
	10	16	407.9882	609.2553
IFNLP	8	14	349.5078	550.1597
	9	15	378.7996	579.7397
	10	16	407.9882	609.2553
NSNLP	8	14	349.5078	550.1597
	9	15	378.7996	579.7397
	10	16	407.9882	609.2553

Here we have considered the weights (0.7, 0.3) for both of the methods WFNLP, WFAGP.

Graph for the average of total cost of 1st item by different methods with different purchase costs. **Graph for the average of total cost of 2nd item by different methods with different purchase costs.** From the figures (Figure-6, Figure-7), we can see that when purchase cost increases, the corresponding average of total cost also increases.

9. Conclusion

In the manuscript we have considered a multi-objective inventory-model under the restriction of the limited storage space. Here we have taken demand as ramp type, deceleration and holding cost as time dependent. In this shortage follow Inventory model we have taken an additional cost known as marketing cost which makes the proposed model more realistic. Shortage follow inventory model is very much attractive for any types of online companies where the companies take pre-booking for their product. It has been seen that if companies take their pre-booking in advance, then their total average cost is much lower. The main purpose of the model is what would be the specific technique for minimizing the total inventory cost. The SFI model gives us more lesser cost in comparison to other traditional inventory model. In this paper we have taken all of the cost parameters as

Intuitionistic triangular fuzzy numbers due to uncertainty. The main objective of the model is to minimize the total average cost. Finally, this model is verified by different optimization techniques as FNLFP, FAGP, WFNLFP, WFAGP, IFNLFP, and NSNLFP.

For future research, the model proposed here can be executed by more practical presupposition like power-demand, probabilistic demand etc. The uncertainty can be controlled by taking triangular fuzzy number, trapezoidal fuzzy number, pentagonal fuzzy number, neutrosophic pentagonal number etc.

Acknowledgement: We would like to convey our sincere gratitude to the department of mathematics, University of Kalyani for their cordial cooperation in financial support through DSE-PURSE (Phase-II). We are also grateful to the Editor and Reviewer for enriching us with their valuable suggestions and comments that make it easier to improve the manuscript.

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Received: Dec. 5, 2021. Accepted: April 3, 2022.